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Remarks on the Bounds of the First Zagreb Index of a Quadrilateral-Free Graph

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Abstract

A graph G is quadrilateral-free if G does not contain a cycle of length 4. The first Zagreb index of a graph G is defined as the sum of the squares of the vertex degrees of G . In this short note, we present upper and lower bounds for the first Zagreb index of a quadrilateral-free graph.

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We consider only finite undirected graphs without loops or multiple edges. Notation and terminology not defined here follow those in [1]. Let $G = (V, E)$

be a graph with n vertices and e edges, where $V = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$. We assume that the vertices in G are arranged such that $\delta(G) = d_G(v_1) := d_1 \leq d_G(v_2) := d_2 \leq \dots \leq d_G(v_n) := d_n = \Delta(G)$, where $d_G(v_i)$, for each i with $1 \leq i \leq n$, is the degree of vertex v_i in G . A graph G is quadrilateral-free if G does not contain a cycle of length 4. We define $C(x, 2)$ as $x(x-1)/2$.

The first Zagreb index was introduced by Gutman and Trinajstić in [3]. For a graph G , its first Zagreb index, denoted $M_1(G)$, is defined as $\sum_{i=1}^n d_G^2(v_i)$. In this short note, we will present an upper bound and a lower bound for the first Zagreb index of a quadrilateral-free graph. The main results of this note are as follows.

Theorem 1 Let G be a quadrilateral-free graph of order n with $\delta \geq 1$. Then

$$[1] \quad M_1 \leq (n - d_k)(n - d_k - 1) + d_k^2 + 3(2e - d_k) - 2(n - 1), \text{ for each } k \text{ with } 1 \leq k \leq n.$$

$$[2] \quad M_1 \geq \frac{(2e - d_k - n + 1)(2e - d_k - 2n + 2)}{n - 1} + d_k^2 + 3(2e - d_k) - 2(n - 1), \text{ for each } k \text{ with } 1 \leq k \leq n.$$

Proof of Theorem 1. Set $N(v_i) := \{v : vv_i, v \in V\}$. Then $|N(v_i)| = d_i$. Füredi established the following inequalities on Page 189 in [2].

$$\begin{aligned} C(n - \Delta, 2) &= (\text{number of pairs of } (V(G) - N(v_n))) \\ &\geq \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} (\text{the number of pairs of } N(v_i) \cap (V(G) - N(v_n))) \\ &\geq \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} C(|N(v_i)| - 1, 2) = \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} C(d_i - 1, 2) \\ &\geq (n - 1)C\left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} (d_i - 1)}{n - 1}, 2\right) \\ &= (n - 1)C\left(\frac{2e - \Delta - n + 1}{n - 1}, 2\right). \end{aligned}$$

Studying Füredi's proofs for the above inequalities in [2], we found that the proofs also imply the following inequalities. For each integer k with $1 \leq k \leq n$,

$$\begin{aligned}
C(n - d_k, 2) &= (\text{number of pairs of } (V(G) - N(v_k))) \\
&\geq \sum_{i=1, i \neq k}^n (\text{the number of pairs of } N(v_i) \cap (V(G) - N(v_k))) \\
&\geq \sum_{i=1, i \neq k}^n C(|N(v_i)| - 1, 2) = \sum_{i=1, i \neq k}^n C(d_i - 1, 2) \\
&\geq (n - 1)C\left(\frac{\sum_{i=1, i \neq k}^n (d_i - 1)}{n - 1}, 2\right) \\
&= (n - 1)C\left(\frac{2e - d_k - n + 1}{n - 1}, 2\right).
\end{aligned}$$

Now from

$$C(n - d_k, 2) \geq \sum_{i=1, i \neq k}^n C(d_i - 1, 2),$$

we can derive that

$$\sum_{i=1, i \neq k}^n d_i^2 \leq 2C(n - d_k, 2) + 3 \sum_{i=1, i \neq k}^n d_i - 2(n - 1).$$

Thus

$$M_1 = \sum_{i=1}^n d_i^2 \leq (n - d_k)(n - d_k - 1) + d_k^2 + 3(2e - d_k) - 2(n - 1).$$

This completes the proof of [1] in Theorem 1.

From

$$\sum_{i=1, i \neq k}^n C(d_i - 1, 2) \geq (n - 1)C\left(\frac{2e - d_k - n + 1}{n - 1}, 2\right),$$

we can derive that

$$\sum_{i=1, i \neq k}^n d_i^2 \geq \frac{(2e - d_k - n + 1)(2e - d_k - 2n + 2)}{n - 1} + 3 \sum_{i=1, i \neq k}^n d_i - 2(n - 1).$$

Thus

$$M_1 = \sum_{i=1}^n d_i^2 \geq \frac{(2e - d_k - n + 1)(2e - d_k - 2n + 2)}{n - 1} + d_k^2 + 3(2e - d_k) - 2(n - 1).$$

This completes the proof of [2] in Theorem 1.

If we let $k = 1$ in Theorem 1, then we have the following corollary.

Corollary 1 Let G be a quadrilateral-free graph of order n with $\delta \geq 1$. Then

$$[1] M_1 \leq (n - \delta)(n - \delta - 1) + \delta^2 + 3(2e - \delta) - 2(n - 1).$$

$$[2] M_1 \geq \frac{(2e - \delta - n + 1)(2e - \delta - 2n + 2)}{n - 1} + \delta^2 + 3(2e - \delta) - 2(n - 1).$$

If we let $k = n$ in Theorem 1, then we have the following corollary.

Corollary 2 Let G be a quadrilateral-free graph of order n with $\delta \geq 1$. Then

$$[1] M_1 \leq (n - \Delta)(n - \Delta - 1) + \Delta^2 + 3(2e - \Delta) - 2(n - 1).$$

$$[2] M_1 \geq \frac{(2e - \Delta - n + 1)(2e - \Delta - 2n + 2)}{n - 1} + \Delta^2 + 3(2e - \Delta) - 2(n - 1).$$

References

- [1] J. A. Bondy and U. S. R. Murty, Graph Theory with Applications, Macmillan, London and Elsevier, New York (1976).
- [2] Z. Füredi, Graphs without quadrilaterals, Journal of Combinatorial Theory B 34 (1983) 187–190.
- [3] I. Gutman and N. Trinajstić, Graph theory and molecular orbitals, total π -electron energy of alternant hydrocarbons, Chem. Phys. Lett. 17 (1972) 535–538.